

IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF WEAKER SECTION (A STUDY FROM SLUM OF GHAZIABAD CITY OF WESTERN (U.P)

Dr. Lajwant Singh

Associate Professor, Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Dayalbagh
Educational Institute (Deemed University), Agra, Utter Pradesh

Abstract:

Development of slum peoples is an ongoing and dynamic process which enables of slum peoples to participate in the decision making in all socio-economic, political and cultural processes in society and enhances their abilities to change the structure and environment that keep them disadvantaged. A development slum person is also crucial for sustaining increasing of job opportunity and economic development of the society. Slum people's development includes both a personal strengthening and enhancement of life chances, and collective participation in efforts to achieve, equality of opportunity and equity between different society. It enhances slum peoples potential at individual and social level of expressions. Development is an essential starting point and a continuing process for realizing the ideals of liberation and freedom for all. Thus when we talk of weaker sections development and slum peoples status, it is important for us recognize that interventions at all levels namely social, educational, economical and political are required and are possible (real change) only if changes take place in existing system and social structure, which are not at all, favorable to the weaker sections today.

Key Words: Governmental Welfare Programme, Scholarship, Job Opportunity, Reservation & Credit Benefits

Introduction:

The concept of globalization is very simple. Globalization, with the free flow of capital, technology goods and services, fuels the expansion, of markets, commerce and trade. The reduction in transport and communication costs, crumbling of artificial barriers to the movement of goods and factors of production has led to a closer integration of economy development of the world.

Globalization is profoundly affecting the lives of people around the world. It is a set of processes in which capital, technology, people, goods and information move relentlessly across the inherited map of political boundaries, and through which the interdependence of societies over vast distances and ever shortening time frames has been intensified. This compression of time and space across a board range of human activities has been made possible by the dramatic decline in the cost of transportation, communication, and production, and by changes in the formal rules that once established substantial barriers against flows across borders. Globalization is multidimensional process of socio-cultural, economic and political transformation. It also has its impact on the environment as well as on human physical and social well being. The whole world is now interconnected in the context of socio-cultural, economic and political currents. It has indeed affected almost each society of the world, but there is a difference in the degree of its impact on different societies and within various sections of the society.

An important dimension of the process of globalization is the gradual spread of ideas and values. Globalization has been opening of idea and values. Globalization has been opening up prospects for inevitable changes concerning development as well as

posing challenges to certain sections of the society. It is not a new phenomenon for the twenty one century yet it is being treated as a most recent, mainly because certain aspects of globalization have posed several challenging threats to the developing and under developed countries primarily in generating social and economic inequalities. And specially points of view of inequality and poverty and their potential impacts on slum dwellers, lots of debates are raging on, yet concluding have been very hard to arrive at. The United Nation estimates that the rural populations have reached their peak, but that there will be a further two billion urban settlers in the next thirty years. About 70% of these will live in slum area. Poor person are in the process of migrating to the unwelcoming town and cities in Asia, Africa, Lattin America. In addition to this, there isa growing number of immigrants to the developed countries such as Germany, France, Canada, United Kingdom, United states of America. For many peoples this new diversity is exciting, even empowering, but for some it is disquieting and disempowering. They fear that their country is becoming fragmented, their values lost as growing numbers of immigrants bring new customs displacing local culture. Some even fore see a nightmarish scenario of cultural homogenization with diverse national cultures giving way to a world dominated by western values and symbols.

Economic attainment and the wellbeing of individuals are crucially dependent on the status of employment and access to resources. All the most elementary level, the status of employment of household members, their expenditure, and ownership of assets determine a household's economic status, which to a very large extent determines the individual's access to resources.

The role of slum areas in shaping the image of a city is important to its future. Many cities at least pay lip service to poverty reduction and officials are mostly genuine in their efforts to improve their society and cities. The existence of slums, inequality and a poor or polluted urban environment is seen as a prime deterrent to international competitiveness and to the location choices international firms and events such as the Olympic Games.

Asia has about 60% of the world's slum dwellers, with India having 18% slum population of the world. Africa has about 21%, but this growing quickly. Latin America has 14%. In 2001, 924 million people or 31.9% of the world's urban population lived in slums. The majority of them were in the develop regions, accounting for 43% of the Urban population, in comparison to 6% in developed regions. The true problem to be tackled, however, is not the visibility of the poor but the condition of poor people. Lack of income lowers life chances directly and in a number of indirect, subtle ways. Poor health and lack of education are major impediments to individuals improving their circumstances and moving out of poverty.

A total of 42.6 million people living in 8.3 million households have been enumerated in slums of 640 towns and cities spared across 26 States and Union Territories in the census of 2001. The slum population constitutes 4.2% of the total population of the country.

Development of Slums Area:

The development is usually accompanied by the under development. Development of mega cities is culminated in to divide of weaker section in slum area. The biggest slum area India is located in out of the most industrial city as: Mumbai, Kolkata, Kanpur, Varanasi, NCR etc. In fact, In fact, while many of the larger cities do have these problems, the reality is far more complex. Most cities are vibrant and dynamic places, each with their own unique character. If not too crippled by the urban externalities congestion, pollution and crime, they have interesting street scrapes,

workspaces and residential spaces in which the majority is able to make an acceptable income and obtain an education, if they wish, while enjoying a better standard of living at a considerable lower risk of death and starvation than their rural counterparts. One important aspect that must be noted is that slums are not the socio-economic wastelands of the popular imagination at all, but provide affordable labor, social networks and residential space however intolerable the standard of living might be. Therefore, the nation of clumsy slum clearance may have adverse effects on the embedded sense of community participation, complex political fabric and networks of support. Globalization has become an active factor in the formation of cities as well as for the formation of slums. It plays a key role in the demographic changes as well as in the policy making. It is clearly putting forth several challenges to the policy makers to address the multifarious problems that may arise due to the rising inequality as well as the growing population.

There are many different meaning and definition of globalization, but the principal underlying idea basically acknowledges the progressive integration of economics and societies. It is driven by new technologies, new economic relationship and the impact of a wide range of national as well as international actors which includes governments, NGO's and international organizations, business, labour and civil society. "Globalization can be thought of as a process which embodies a transformation in the spatial organization of social relations and transactions assessed in terms of their extensity, intensity, velocity and impact generating transcontinental or interregional flows and networks of activity, interaction, and the exercise of power". Globalization is multiple and covers most areas of social life and human relations such as economy, polity, culture and ideology. Since globalization is a work in progress, the end result is yet under mind.

The globalization has brought with it several debates about its socio-economic, political and cultural implications. One of the most debated issues has been the increasing gap between poor and rich countries and within a country. As the number of slums has been increasing the world over, within the developing nations particularly India, percentage of population residing in slums is also increasing. Slum dwellers are mostly deprived of several opportunities which the city dwellers have access. Similarly, they remain confined to locally paid jobs, and traditional culture. Globalization starting from the west has been diffusing across the globe but the effect may remain diluted from Centre to periphery and within a country from Urban to Rural and Urban Centre to urban periphery where the slums are located. There may be difference in the impact of globalization on the development of slums of different in India or elsewhere. One of the major factors responsible in the spread of globalization has been media. Particularly, Television, Internet and Mobile.

Development of slums to a larger extent depends upon governments initiatives of a country. Equally important is people's participation in the government's development programmes and their self development. With the process of globalization there has been a rapid change in all aspects of the life. This study is to analyze how globalization serves social development in slums. In particular, how globalization serves as diagnostic, prognostic and motivational frames through its effects and espouses elements of development. An understanding of framing of the social development used in slum has important implications for understanding the effectiveness of globalization stimulating social consciousness and mobilizing the society. Globalization has produced some calamitous consequences from human resources, humanity and slums. Globalization is presently a fundamental force that cannot be denied as it affords

obvious benefits to a larger number of people, however, conversely, it threatens life, in a broader sense, society currently manifests diverse ills, and it is postulated that protracted civil and revolutions could isolate governments from there, subjects.

Review of the Relevant Literature:

Various macro as well as micro level studies impact of globalization on the development of weaker sections have been conducted by different social scientists and economists. These main findings have been discussed in the following

1. Thompson (1995): "The media and Modernity" examines the role of global communication networks. While these processes have changed the nature of symbolic exchange and life conditions of people throughout the world, these changes are not necessarily at the expense of local culture. However, global media products can as easily produce antagonism as it can understand.

2. Seghal (1998): "Slum up gradation: Emerging issues and policy Implications" address itself equally to persons and institutions in both developing and industrialized countries. It is hoped that a comparative analysis of this nature will assist the governments of developing countries in their efforts to find appropriate policy approaches through information exchange.

3. Tomlinson (1999): "Globalization and culture" Undertakes an analysis of the complex, ambiguous "lived experience" of global modernity. Tomlinson argues that we can now see a general pattern of the dissolution of links between cultural experience and territorial location. The "Uneven" nature of this experience is discussed in the relation to first and third world societies, among with arguments about the hybridization of cultures, and the special role of communications and media technologies in this process of deterritorialization.

4. Rizzini and Bush (2002): "Globalization and children" say that globalization also describes forces that have produced enormous changes in the lives of children. The United Nations Millennium goals for children set out concrete improvements in such areas as infant and maternal mortality, child poverty and child labor. The authors note that children won't be good informants about the consequences of decisions made by IMF. But they will be best, though still fallible, informants about what it is like to grow up in the Mississippi Delta, the slums of Bombay, or the favelas of Sao Paulo.

Objective of the Study:

The present study is basically an explanatory study, which is based on the primary and as well as secondary data of information for systematization analysis and conclusion. In the regarding impact of globalization development and change in socio-economic, political status of the weaker section in slum. The constitution of India, census of India, relevant Journal, article, books, newspaper and magazines etc., have been made use as secondary data. The main objective of the study is:

- ✓ Changing Social status among weaker section peoples slums of Ghaziabad city,
- ✓ Impact of globalization on economic status of slums dwellers
- ✓ To find out change in cultural life of the weaker section's peoples
- ✓ To create capability to present their position in society effectively
- ✓ To find political and Human Rights awareness of slums peoples

Methodology:

The present study belongs to slums of Ghaziabad city of NCR and western Uttar Pradesh. We obtained the list of Ghaziabad city from the office of Ghaziabad Nagar Nigam. Selected 4 slums area out of 78 slums' the random sampling methods, viz: Jhandapur, Baradari, Kallupura, Visvas Nagar, Sudamapuri.

Fifteen percent population of slum area belongs to the selected four Basti while the remaining 68 percent population of slums belongs to the remaining 78 slums areas. Table 1 show population of selected slums as following

Table 1: Population of Selected Slum's Area

S.No	Name of Slum Area	Total People of Slum's	Percentage of Population	No of Selected Respondents
1	Jhandapur	2370	15.49	47
2	BaradariKallupura	1864	12.18%	37
3	Visvas Nagar	3859	25.23%	77
4	Sudamapuri	7200	47.09%	144
Total		15293	99.99%	305

Above slum's area was selected in consultation with the Nagar Nigam of Ghaziabad. From four slum area we have selected a slum area as Jhamdapur, Baradari Kallupura, Visvas Nagar and Sudamapuri by lottery sampling method. From each slum area, the respondents are selected in proportion to the total number of slum residents in that slum.

Globalization and Social Changes of Weaker Sections:

The social development is defined as a transformation of institutions which promotes good growth, good project and good quality of life. Social development is about putting people at the centre of development. This means a commitment that development processes need to benefit people but not only the poor, but also the recognition that people, and the way they interact in groups and society, and the norms that facilities such interaction, shape development processes.

Social development thus implies the change in social institutions. Progress toward an inclusive society, for example, implies that individuals treat each other fairly in their daily lives, whether in the family, work place, or public office. Social cohesion is enhanced when peaceful and safe environment within neighborhoods and communities are created. Social accountability exists to the extent that citizens' voices are expressed, and heard by the authorities. Formal institutional reform for example, the provision of legally enshrined rights, better law enforcement or more participatory governance are part of the process by which institutional change is achieved, changing the way people relate to people is an equally important part of this.

For the present study, social development of weaker section peoples can be operationalized as, "increase in supply of food, clothing, housing and social security which is required in order to fulfill the aspirations of slum dwellers". This also includes the increasing in employments, education, and changing the various of tradition occupation and many provides facilities as water supply, health facilities, hygiene, sanitation and improvement of working, living environment. It further includes the improvement in proper supply of electricity, literacy rate, quality of relationship, increasing in earning capacity, employment opportunities, possession of assets, and use of electronic items. Change in eating habit, dressing habit, cultural intermixing and the spreading of awareness about government schemes, rights and democracy, intimacy level with politician or parties, awareness about national and international issues. The following table shows change wedding trend in slum peoples.

Table 2: Change of trend in Wedding Venue

S.No	Which Wedding Venue Did You Use	Frequency (F)	Percentage
1	Hire banquet Hall	97	32.0%
2	Hire Marriage Home	83	27.0
3	Hire Hotel	7	2.0%
4	No Change	118	39.0%

	Total	305	100%
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It made clear of above table there is a change of wedding venue? When this question was put forth before respondents then 32.0% respondents said they hired a Banquet Hall for marriage. 27.0% respondents gave answer that they hired marriage Hall. And 2.0% respondents said that they hired Hotel for marriage. It indicates that they are under the influence of globalization. 39.0% respondent said that there is no change in marriage venue.

Figure 1: Change of trend in Wedding Venue

This study analysis the impact of globaloization on the mode of cooking food. The sample size 305 respondent use new technological instrument for cooking the food. Table No.3 it made clear.

Table 3: Different type's mode of cooking food

S.No	Types Mode of Cooking Food	Frequency (F)	Percentage
1	Coal/wood, Chulha	203	66%
2	Gass	79	26%
3	Heater	23	8%
	Total	305	100%

Figure 2: Different type's mode of cooking food

When the respondent were asked about the method by which they cook food, then 66% respondent replied that they cook food by using coal/wood, chulha. This is the largest ratio when compared to others. The respondent of this category were found to be affected by the smoke, as it could be noted that they had respiratory problems and eye

related ailments. So the government should provide them with gas at very subsidized rates. However, there were 26% respondents who used gas for cooking food. On the other hand, there were 8% respondents who use electric heater for cooking because they do not have money to buy gas. It should also be that the respondents of this category are highly prone to getting shocked, that even may cause death while cooking on the electric heater.

Educational Development through Globalization:

In the present study analysis the impact of globalization on educational status of slums. The sample consisted of 305 respondents. Table No. 2 it make clear.

Table 4: Education Received by the slum's

S.No	Types of Education	Frequency of Student	Percentage (%)
1	General Education	174	57.05%
2	Professional Education	9	2.96%
3	Technical Education	11	3.61%
4	Vocational Education	7	2.29%
5	No any Education	104	34.09%
Total		305	100%

Figure 3: Education Received by the slum's

The above table show the type of education received by the respondents 57.05% respondents got general education, 3.61 respondents got technical education, 34.09% persons did not get any type education which means that they are illiterate person and they were not aware about education. The other reasons they reported was the absence of schools nearby are and, due to backwardness and lack of money they were unable to send in their children's to distant of school, 2.29% respondents had taken vocational education, 2.96% had taken professional education. But they said that this type of education was very expensive and that they were not in the financial situation to bear the expenses of it. Majority of slum dwellers are enrolled in general education due to their poor social and economic background.

Level of Education in Slum's Area:

Education is the systematic instruction of selected knowledge to develop the mental powers and general awareness of the people. When provided with adequate education, Human can progress their knowledge, and ability to create wealth and enjoy it wisely, much faster than any previous generation.

Education plays a very important role in the social development of an individual as well as in developing his/her identity in the global context. Where there is education there is chance of better standards of living; education increases the potential wages for an individual. A government can easily administer its policies if the people of the given region are educated. The main indicator of poverty eradication in a changing society is improving access to health and access to education. Education is essential for a person to take care of his health and his environment. Therefore, the educational framework of the particular area makes a major impact on the minds of the people. The table No. 5 is clear educational level of slum peoples.

Table 5: Educational level of slum people's

S.No	In Which Class do They Study	Male	Female
1	Illiterate	40(13%)	61(20%)
2	Class 1-5	68(22%)	53(17%)
3	Class 6-12	39(13)	26(9%)
4	Graduate and above	11(4%)	7(2%)
Total		305	

Figure 4: Educational level of slum people's

Show the above table 13% boys were illiterate and 20% girls were same the number of school going class 1-5, girls were 17% and the boys were 22%, when compared to the boys for the same class range the number of girls were less; these girls were interested in going to school due to the policies of free education, mid-day meal scheme, free uniforms and due to the availability of scholarship. They were able to get admission in primary education. 9.0% girls took study in class 6-12 and this number was very less as compared to boys due to lack of awareness, and the dropout rate of girls from the class 6-12 on observing the data enrollment in graduate of girls 2.0% it was half that of boys.

Economic development of Slum Peoples:

The economics of societies of the world are becoming increasingly interdependent. Trade and capital flow, migration, scientific and technological innovations, communications and cultural exchanges are shaping the global community. Globalization contributes to economic growth in developed and developing countries through increased specialization and the principle of comparative advantage.

The Government of India has been running many schemes for economic development of slums like "Integrated Low cost sanitation programme in Urban areas". This scheme is formulated by 'Suchitwhwa Mission, Kerala as a part of the centrally sponsored scheme of Integrated Low cost sanitation programme. Under this scheme, a portion of the targeted pour flush individual latrine tank will be replaced by Bio-Digestion chamber which will be more hygienic. Other programmes for slum's development are Rajeev Awas Yojana, Urban self Employment Programme (USEP), urban Women self help programme (UWSP), Urban Wage Employment Programme (UWEP), Skill Training Employment Promotion Amongst Urban Poor (STEP-UP) Kaushal Training Prashikshan Programme (KTPP), Urban Community Development Network (UCDN), Integrated Housing and slum Development Programme (IHSDP), slum improvement schemes. Under this scheme.'

Providing the basic amenities like drinking water, streetlights, community toilet, community bathroom, U.G.D. storm water Drain, National Slum Development Programme (NSDP) have been induced.

Employment Opportunities for Slum's People's:

It refers to availability of sufficient job opportunities to be employed for increasing income and it is of two types one is formal and other one is informal. Formal means that the person are getting employment through formal agencies like government organizations, any registered company or through the schemes launched by the government like Rajiv Awas Yojana (RAY.2011) etc. On the contrary, informal employment opportunities mean that people are working in factories, at traders place, at shop's in forms etc. Where they are getting low wages and have to work for hours under inadequate safety measures, they are working because they do not have any other options but with the advent of globalization and with the coming of multinational companies the quality employment is generated as these companies abide by all the norms, give proper wages in time, having fixed working hours and take care of most of the safety measures so, it is the positive impact of globalization that the quality of employment has been generated.

The Shrinking public sector employment overcrowding in formal sectors, increased competition for sources and service, and a growing survivalist orientation on the part of many urban residents re-localizes the ways in which people structure every day work relationships. The growth in the global labor force has imposed enormous strains on Urban settings, especially on employment and housing. As the formal sector has failed to meet such demands, the informal sector has taken up the slack. It is now generally accepted that the economic activity and employment in the urban informal sector are extremely important in developing countries where population and demand for jobs, goods and services are typically growing more quickly than national averages and too quickly for formal job creation to cope with.

Indeed, years of structural adjustment and reduction in government employment have reduced formal sector job opportunities in many Urban areas. The informal sector creates many of the jobs needed by the growing work force and compensates for much of the formal sector's failure to provide goods and services. It is predominant in slum neighborhoods but occurs in higher income areas, as well. The capitalist producers of the formal sector can gain through exploiting informal sector workers. Through it, they can reduce the costs of raw materials and inputs for formal-sector production, and they can keep formal sector labor costs lower by providing wage goods to formal-sector worker more cheaply than the formal sector itself can generate.

Slum People's and Contributor of Family Income:

In this study analysis the economic impact of globalization. Following issues have been raised to see the impact of globalization on economic development of slum peoples. The below table No.-6 its make clear

Table 6: Contribution in family income

S.No	Who the Main Contributor in Family Income	Frequency(f)	Percentage
1	Adults	139	46%
2	Father	88	29%
3	Husband or wife(Spouse)	49	16%
4	Children	29	9%
Total		305	100%

Figure 5: Contribution in family income

The 46% respondents said that they themselves contribute to their family income because they are adults and have to take care of their family. However, there were 29% respondents who said that their father was main contributor of income in their family. Whereas, there were 16% respondent who said that, their husband or wife any one is the main contributor of income in the family. Furthermore, there were 9% respondents who said the main contributor of their family income. And their children in any conditions, because respondent's income was not sufficient to run the family, so they have to send their children out for work to fulfill the basic requirements of the family.

Political Awareness About Weaker Section People's:

The political development and awareness of different parts of the world are undergoing a transformation due to the fact that countries need to establish relationships with each other to function in certain ways to improve their economic status, to foster political as well as religious ideologies and to solve various problems that cut across borders like energy imbalances, epidemics, pollution, global warming, terrorism, depletion of the resources and global insecurity, Numerous slums that have dotted the planet are also a lingering issue.

Political organization today is no longer discrete worlds. Growing enmeshment in regional and global orders and the proliferation of trans border problems has created a plurality of diverse and over lapping groups which span borders binding together directly and indirectly the fate of communities in different locations and regions of the globe.

The contemporary world is no longer a world of closed communities with mutually impenetrable ways of thought, self-sufficient economics and ideally sovereign states. This is not to assert that territorial political. Communities are becoming obsolete

but, rather, to recognize that they are nested within global, regional and transitional communities of fame identity, association, and solidarity. Political community today is being transformed to accord with a world of ruptured boundaries.

Awareness of Fundamental Rights of Slum Peoples:

To accept a set of rights is to approve a distribution of freedom and authority, and so to endorse a certain view. Awareness of rights cannot there should be open discussion of public affairs, openness in government enhances the accountability of government increases the participation of members of the community in democratic process leading to better informed decision-making, and right to information improves public administration and the quality of government and decision making.

It is not generally considered necessary that a right should be understood by the holder of that right; thus rights may be reconised on behalf of another, such as children's rights or the rights of people declared mentally incompetent to understand their rights. However, rights must be understood by someone in order to have legal existence, so the understanding of rights is a social prerequisite for the existence of rights.

In this study analysis the impact of globalization on political life of slum people's. Various question have been asked and their responses have been table No.7

Table 7: Slum people's awareness of fundamental rights

S.No	Aware about the Fundamental Rights enshrined in the constitution	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
1	Aware	127	42%
2	Not aware	178	58%
Total		305	100%

Cleared the above table 42.0% said they were aware about their fundamental rights, like right to equality, right to freedom, rights against exploitation etc. And they know the rights that were given by the constitution. But 58.0% respondents gave negative reply and said they were not aware about fundament and human rights. So it is pertinent for the government to sanction certain measures to enhance the legal literacy of these people so that they may know about their fundamental and Human Right.

Conclusion:

Conclude of this study globalization plays a major and important role in process of social change and development in India. Globalization has improved the social, educational, economical, political aspects of slum peoples life. The slum people's are now more connected with the whole world and they feel comfortable about it.

Globalization has a positive impact on the slum's in the context of economic and education; it has increased and spread more awareness about the importance of education in improving a people's life. Now parents have become more concerned about their children's receiving good education and they chose best school and medium for future of their children. The main earning persons in the slums are the father feels more burdens to fulfill his duties for his family, but the income is not sufficient to fulfill the need of the family. The females of slum area want to earn money and want to contribute or play their part in the family. The children are aware about the use of internet and they know the benefits of ICT.

Due this political impact of globalization knowledge about democracy has increased, majority of the slum dwellers are satisfied by the democratic from of government. Now, their level of knowledge about international organization has increased. More ever, impact of globalization on political life of slums has increased the awareness about human Rights. Slum Persons want to solve their problems with the

help of their political representatives. They want that the government should make policies in their favor so in this way they support the political party that is most favorable to them.

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